

Insights from the In silico docking study of *CHRYSOSPENOL* with TNF- α of Parenchyma of Testes

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ABSTRACT:

Introduction: A cytokine that is thought to serve as the primary mediator in the inflammatory process is tumor necrosis factor, also known as (TNF). It is involved in the development of various diseases including stress-induced damages in gonadal organs that may lead to infertility. Men are at risk of infertility for the following reasons: Ageing, smoking, alcohol overconsumption, being overweight or obese, and exposure to toxins. These may cause morphological abnormalities in sperm as a result of the secretory malfunction of the Leydig and Sertoli cells. Research findings show that the number of macrophages and apoptotic germ cells expressing Tumor necrosis factor (TNF) receptor 1 are increased in all kinds of inflammatory changes.

Objective: To establish the efficacy of Chrysofenol, a phytochemical component of *Sphaeranthus amaranthoides* targeting TNF- α in apoptosis of parenchyma of testes by Molecular docking analysis.

Method: Chrysofenol present in *Sphaeranthus amaranthoides* is identified. Before docking begins, the three-dimensional model of the TNF-alpha the target ,is extracted from the repository and refined. Potency of the herb is screened based on the binding of the phytochemical with the target on the protein.

Results: Chrysofenol has a high degree of free energy(-5.87 kcal/mol).and three interactions with the target TNF-alpha's core active amino acid residues.

Conclusion: *Sphaeranthus amaranthoides* would possess potent anti-inflammatory action which prevents the gonadal damages thus beneficial in treating infertility.

Keywords : Inflammation, TNF-alpha, Infertility, *Sphaeranthus amaranthoides*, Sertoli cells, Chrysofenol

1.INTRODUCTION:

Male reproductive function can be readily impacted by infectious and inflammatory illnesses, which can lead to infertility. Male infertility is associated with increased levels of proinflammatory cytokines in semen and testis. Induction or suppression of inflammation in any part of the body is carried out by cytokines^[1]. Inflammation is elicited by oxidative stress which is known to cause negative impacts on steroidogenesis and impairs sperm function^[2].

Cytokines are small membrane-bound protein based cell signalling molecules which are responsible for cell-cell communication in immune responses. Cytokines are normally found in male genital tract and are present in seminal plasma. One of the inflammatory cytokines is Tumor Necrosis Factor alpha also known as (TNF alpha)^[3]. It is primarily secreted by activated immune cells such as macrophages, lymphocytes and mast cells during acute inflammation and is responsible for cell signaling events which leads to necrosis or apoptosis^[4]. Receptors of TNF-alpha are present in Sertoli cells and Leydig cells, hence it is capable of influencing the functions of these cells.

Sertoli cells are special cells which line the epithelial layer of seminiferous tubules. It is vital for spermatogenesis^[5]. Leydig cells are also known as testicular interstitial cells and are present between the seminiferous tubules. Being responsible for biosynthesis of androgens Leydig cells play a critical role in sperm production and secondary sexual characteristics^[6]. Many cases of male infertility face acute inflammation of genitourinary tract. Spermatogenesis is affected by inflammation which is often associated with oxidative stress that causes damage to the sperm DNA and induces apoptosis in sperm. Increased levels of TNF-alpha is seen in cases of oligozoospermic patients which is an indicator of testicular damage^[7]. The seminal Plasma levels of TNF-alpha are found to be elevated in cases of unexplained infertility^[8].

Siddha system of medicine has been in practice for over thousands of years in treatment of several diseases and conditions using Natural products that are plant, mineral and animal based. It was devised by 18 divine souls Siddhars who have classified diseases as 4448 with the immense medical knowledge attained through their spiritual and yogic practices. Herbal therapeutics have become renowned in treatment of acute and chronic conditions owing to its properties like the presence of many bioactive compounds, lesser side effects, non-toxicity and safe when taken in prescribed doses^[9]. It has been mentioned in Siddha literatures that the herb *Sphaeranthus amaranthoides* known as "Sivakarantjai" can be administered for male infertility. One potential method for classifying inhibitors would be to examine substances with a herbal origin that have been reported in the literature. Such plant-derived bioactive substances are certain to provide such a therapeutic effect^[10]. In order to achieve this, we used a virtual screening campaign to dock Chrysofenol, which is contained in *Sphaeranthus amaranthoides* and has been linked to male sterility in the Siddha text, against TNF-alpha in order to forecast its pharmacological value and strong anti-inflammatory effect.

***Sphaeranthus amaranthoides*:**

It is a small procumbent herb belonging to the family Asteraceae. The whole plant is of high medicinal value. "Sivakarantjai" – the rejuvenator herb has high antioxidant and wound healing activity^[11]. *Sphaeranthus* also possess anti-inflammatory, anti-microbial, anti-mutagenic, anti-diarrhoeal, anti-diabetic, analgesic and hepatoprotective effects^[12]. It has been used in Siddha medicine to treat male infertility, eczema, skin diseases, wounds, as mentioned in the literature^[13].

Anti-inflammatory activity:

Several medicinal properties including anti-inflammatory activity can be attributed to the phytochemicals present in Sivakarantjai. Phytochemical screening studies have revealed that this contains^[14]. A study done using GC-MS analysis identified and revealed the presence of 15 different phytochemicals that justifies the application of this plant in Siddha herbal therapeutics to treat male infertility and several other diseases that develop as a result of inflammation^[15]. It was discovered to have an inhibitory effect during the second phase of acute inflammation in a study assessing its anti-inflammatory action using Carrageenan-induced hind paw inflammation in Wistar rat models. ^[16] Wound healing is a complex process involving

various cells, cytokines, (TNF) and mediators. During inflammatory stage macrophage secretes TNF α to stimulate fibroblast and keratinocytes^[17]. In a study performed on Guinea pigs to evaluate the wound healing properties of *Sphaeranthus amaranthoides*, it was found that in 15 days of treatment with the extract of *Sphaeranthus amaranthoides*, the Guinea pigs showed effective healing of 100%^[18]. It can be attributed to promising anti-inflammatory activity that can possibly inhibit the inflammation induced by increased levels of TNF- α in the testes and thereby can prove to be beneficial in treating male infertility cases. Docking studies pave way to establish the same with the aid of advanced software and technologies by justifying the potency of the herbs which will be screened based on the binding of the phytochemicals with the target present on the protein.

Hence we aim to evident the promising anti-inflammatory effect of Chryso-splenol existing in *Sphaeranthus amaranthoides* affecting TNF- α in apoptosis of parenchyma of testes.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

2.1. Ligand used:

Ligand in 2D

Ligand in 3D

Figure:1 Two-dimensional and three-dimensional structural representation of Chryso-splenol, the flavonoid phytochemical isolated from *Sphaeranthus amaranthoides*. The hydroxyl groups and aromatic rings are highlighted, which contribute to hydrogen bonding and π - π interactions during docking with TNF- α .

2.2:Target protein:

The target protein TNF- α 's crystalline structure was obtained from the protein data bank, and necessary missing hydrogen atoms were inserted after the protein was cleaned up. The Autodock algorithm assessed the lead molecules' various orientations with regard to the target protein, and the interaction study analysis was used to determine the optimal dock pose.

Figure:2 Crystalline structure of TNF- α (PDB ID: 2AZ5) showing the trimeric arrangement of monomers. The active site residues (Leu57, Tyr59, Tyr119, Gly121, Tyr151) are indicated, which are critical for ligand binding and cytokine signaling.

2.3.Methodology:

Chrysosplenol, the phytocomponent that was recovered, underwent docking calculations against the target protein. With the use of AutoDock tools, necessary hydrogen atoms, Kollman unified atom type charges, and solvation parameters were introduced (Morris, Goodsell et al., 1998). Using the Autogrid program, affinity (grid) maps with $\times\times$ Å grid points and 0.375 Å spacing were produced (Morris, Goodsell et al., 1998). The van der Waals and electrostatic components were computed using AutoDock parameter set- and distance-dependent dielectric functions, respectively. The Lamarckian genetic algorithm (LGA) and the Solis & Wets local search technique (Solis and Wets, 1981) were used to carry out docking simulations. The ligand molecules' initial orientation, location, and torsions were all randomly determined. During docking, all rotatable torsions were freed. Every docking experiment was the result of two separate runs that were intended to end after a maximum of 250000 energy assessments. 150 people were the target population. A translational step of 0.2 Å and quaternion and torsion steps of 5 were used in the search.

3.RESULTS

Fig:3 Docking pose of Chrysosplenol within the active site of TNF- α (PDB ID: 2AZ5). Hydrogen bond interactions are observed with Tyr59, Gln61, Tyr119, Leu120, and Tyr151, confirming stable ligand–protein binding. The visualization demonstrates the orientation of Chrysosplenol relative to the receptor pocket.

Table 1. The molecular characteristics of the ligand Chrysosplenol

Ligand	Molar weight g/mol	Molecular Formula	H Bond Donor	H Bond Acceptor	Rotatable bonds
Chrysosplenol	360.3 g/mol	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₈	3	8	4

Table 2. Results of molecular docking studies of the Chrysosplenol against TNF-alpha (2AZ5)

Name of the Ligand	Estimated Free Energy of Binding	Estimated Inhibition Constant, Ki	Electrostatic Energy	Total Intermolecular Energy	Interaction Surface
Chrysosplenol	-5.87 kcal/mol	49.77 μ M	-0.05 kcal/mol	-6.10 kcal/mol	557.451

After keen observation of the residues following aminoacids form hydrogen bond interactions 59 TYR, 61 GLN, 119 TYR, 120 LEU and 151 TYR. Chrysosplenol is estimated to possess a high level of free energy (-5.87 kcal/mol. It aids in establishing the binding efficacy between the chosen ligand (Chrysosplenol) and chosen target (TNF-alpha). Thus negative the energy , stronger the protein ligand complex.

Table 3. Interaction of lead amino acid molecules of Chrysosplenol against TNF-alpha (2AZ5)

Ligand	Interactions	Aminoacid Residue Interaction				
Chrysosplenol	3	59 TYR	61 GLN	119 TYR	120 LEU	151 TYR

From the herb, the bioactive substance chystoplenol was extracted. According to the herb's published research, the phytochemical can interact up to three times with the target TNF-alpha's core active amino acid residues. Chrysosplenol, which is derived from *Sphaeranthus amaranthoides* compound, was found to exhibit promising anti-inflammatory activity based on the computational analysis results, which indicated that this bio-active compound reveals important affinity for binding against the target enzyme the production of TNF by interacting with active amino acids that are present on the active site.

4. DISCUSSION:

Docking analysis is a cornerstone of modern computational drug discovery, providing predictive insights into how small molecules interact with macromolecular targets[19]. In the present study, Chrysosplenol a flavonoid phytochemical derived from *Sphaeranthus amaranthoides* was docked against TNF- α , a cytokine central to inflammatory cascades in the male reproductive system(Figure 3). The results demonstrated favorable binding free energy and multiple hydrogen bond interactions with critical amino acid residues, suggesting that Chrysosplenol could act as a potent inhibitor of TNF- α activity. Expanding upon these findings requires a multi-layered discussion that integrates molecular biology, pharmacology, ethnomedicine, and translational research.

TNF- α is a pleiotropic cytokine implicated in diverse cellular processes including apoptosis, necrosis, and immune regulation [20]. Within the testes, TNF- α is secreted by macrophages, Sertoli cells, and Leydig cells under conditions of stress or infection that is released after proteolytic cleavage by TNF-alpha converting enzyme [21]. Elevated TNF- α levels have been consistently associated with impaired spermatogenesis, DNA fragmentation in spermatozoa, and reduced steroidogenesis. The cytokine exerts its effects via TNF receptor 1 (TNFR1), which activates downstream signaling pathways such as NF- κ B and MAPK [22]. These pathways culminate in the transcription of pro-inflammatory genes, perpetuating oxidative stress and cellular apoptosis. Thus, inhibition of TNF- α represents a rational therapeutic strategy for mitigating testicular inflammation and preserving fertility[23].

Chrysosplenol belongs to the flavonoid class of polyphenolic compounds, known for their antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. Structurally, Chrysosplenol contains multiple hydroxyl groups that facilitate hydrogen bonding with protein residues, enhancing its binding affinity. The docking results revealed interactions with residues Tyr59, Gln61, Tyr119, Leu120, and Tyr151 amino acids located within the active site of TNF- α (Table 3). These interactions are critical because they may sterically hinder TNF- α from binding to its receptor, thereby attenuating downstream signalling [24]. The negative binding free energy is -5.87

kcal/mol (Table 2) and this negative energy further supports the stability of the Chrysosplenol–TNF- α complex [25].

Current clinical practice employs biologics such as infliximab, etanercept, and adalimumab to neutralize TNF- α activity. While effective, these agents are expensive, require parenteral administration, and carry risks of immunosuppression. In contrast, plant-derived compounds like Chrysosplenol offer a potentially safer and more accessible alternative. Although the binding affinity of Chrysosplenol is modest compared to monoclonal antibodies, its polyphenolic nature may confer additional antioxidant benefits, thereby addressing both inflammation and oxidative stress simultaneously. This dual mechanism could be particularly advantageous in the context of male infertility, where oxidative damage to sperm DNA is a major contributor.

The Siddha system of medicine emphasizes holistic treatment using plant-based formulations. *Sphaeranthus amaranthoides*, known as “Sivakaranthai,” has long been prescribed for male infertility, skin disorders, and inflammatory conditions [26]. The present docking study provides molecular validation for these traditional claims. By demonstrating that Chrysosplenol binds effectively to TNF- α , the study bridges ancient ethnomedical knowledge with modern computational pharmacology. This integration not only strengthens the credibility of Siddha medicine but also opens avenues for developing standardized herbal formulations that can be subjected to rigorous clinical testing.

Hydrogen bonding plays a pivotal role in stabilizing protein-ligand complexes [27]. The observed interactions between Chrysosplenol and TNF- α residues suggest that the compound may interfere with the trimerization of TNF- α or its binding to TNFR1. Such interference could prevent the recruitment of adaptor proteins like TRADD and FADD, thereby blocking the initiation of apoptotic cascades. Additionally, by modulating NF- κ B activation, Chrysosplenol may reduce the transcription of pro-inflammatory cytokines, creating a more favorable microenvironment for spermatogenesis. These mechanistic insights underscore the therapeutic potential of Chrysosplenol in reproductive immunology.

The docking simulations employed AutoDock tools, which utilize the Lamarckian genetic algorithm to explore conformational space. While docking provides valuable predictions, it is inherently limited by the static nature of protein structures and the absence of solvent dynamics. Real biological systems are dynamic, with proteins undergoing conformational changes upon ligand binding. Therefore, molecular dynamics (MD) simulations should complement docking studies to assess the stability of the Chrysosplenol–TNF- α complex over time. Additionally, free energy perturbation (FEP) calculations could provide more accurate estimates of binding affinity [28,29].

5. Study limitations:

The study focused exclusively on Chrysosplenol, whereas *Sphaeranthus amaranthoides* contains multiple bioactive compounds. A comprehensive docking analysis of all phytochemicals could reveal synergistic interactions that enhance therapeutic efficacy. Furthermore, ADMET (Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, Excretion, and Toxicity) profiling is essential to predict the pharmacokinetic behavior of Chrysosplenol. In vivo studies using animal models of testicular inflammation would provide empirical validation of the docking results. Ultimately, clinical trials are necessary to establish safety and efficacy in human populations.

6. Conclusion:

Thus the mention of *Sphaeranthus amaranthoides* in treatment of male infertility in Siddha literature has been established by proving its anti-inflammatory activity through In Silico Study on the phytochemical Chrysosplenol of *Sphaeranthus amaranthoides* targeting TNF- α in apoptosis of parenchyma of testes. Siddha system of medicine is a potential valuable source for Herbal therapeutics that are known for being safe with high efficacy and medicinal value due to the presence of several bio-active phytochemicals. Results of this present study concludes that the herb *Sphaeranthus amaranthoides* has promising anti-inflammatory activity by inhibiting TNF-alpha and thereby could be effective in treating male infertility.

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